

MEDICAL SCIENCES

IMMUNOTHERAPY STRATEGIES IN DIFFERENT TYPES OF PRIMARY IMMUNODEFICIENCY PATIENTS

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Abstract

Primary immunodeficiencies (PIDs) are a heterogeneous group of congenital immune disorders characterized by increased susceptibility to infections, autoimmune manifestations, and allergic conditions. This study presents a retrospective analysis of immunotherapeutic strategies applied to patients with PIDs treated at the Azerbaijan Medical University between 2010 and 2025. Diagnoses were made in accordance with the classifications proposed by the International Union of Immunological Societies (IUIS) and the European Society of Immunodeficiencies (ESID). Following genetic testing, diagnoses were further refined based on the most recent guidelines: Human Congenital Immunodeficiencies: 2024 Update of the International Union of Experts on the Classification of Diseases. Treatment protocols were selected based on the type and severity of immune dysfunction. The findings highlight the importance of targeted therapies such as immunoglobulin replacement therapy, cytokine modulation and immunostimulatory drugs tailored to specific PID subtypes.

Keywords: Primary immunodeficiencies, immunotherapy, Azerbaijani patients.

Introduction:

Primary immunodeficiencies (PIDs) encompass over 450 genetically determined disorders of the immune system, presenting with a broad spectrum of clinical features such as recurrent skin, lung and intestinal infections, autoimmunity, malignancies, and allergic manifestations [6, 11, 13, 15, 19]. The variability in clinical expression depends on the underlying immune defect. The overarching treatment goal is to alleviate symptoms, prevent infections, and restore immune function [17].

Unlike acquired immunodeficiencies, which are often transient, congenital forms typically require life-long management [11]. Immunotherapy has become central to PID treatment, offering targeted interventions based on specific immune deficits [4, 13]. Advances in molecular diagnostics and genetic testing have enabled precision therapies for a growing number of PID subtypes.

The primary objective of immunotherapy in PID is to compensate for immune deficiencies or modulate inappropriate immune responses. Available treatments include immunoglobulin replacement, cytokine therapy, thymic peptides, and hematopoietic stem cell transplantation (HSCT) [1, 12, 14, 17].

Immunoglobulin therapy administered intravenously (IVIG) or subcutaneously (SCIG) remains foundational, particularly in antibody-deficient patients [14, 16–19]. Immunoglobulins neutralize pathogens, enhance phagocytosis, and modulate immune cell activity across various innate and adaptive immune compartments [7, 11, 12, 14, 19].

Thymic peptides have also shown promise in supporting T-cell development and immune homeostasis, especially in cases like DiGeorge syndrome [3, 9].

HSCT remains the most effective and often the only treatment for severe or life-threatening combined forms of PID [6, 8, 9, 17]. Unfortunately, the complexity and high cost of this method are associated with the search for suitable donors, the involvement of highly qualified specialists, the need for long-term administration of immunomodulatory and immunosuppressive drugs, and special care conditions for these patients. Even under optimal circumstances, the success rate of stem cell transplantation, according to data from various countries, reaches 50–80%. A joint study by European PID centers participating in a registry for stem cell transplantation in severe combined immunodeficiencies (SCID) and other immunodeficiency disorders includes data from 37 centers in 18 countries (1968–1999). In SCID, 3-year survival with sustained engraftment was significantly better after HLA-identical than mismatched transplantation (77%), and survival improved over time. Currently, the 5-year survival rate for children with PID who received transplants from genotypically identical donors is as high as 90% [1, 4].

Methods:

A retrospective review was conducted of more than 170 PID patients diagnosed and treated between 2010 and 2025 at Azerbaijan Medical University. Diagnoses were established in accordance with classification systems proposed by the International Union of Immunological Societies (IUIS) and the European So-

ciety for Immunodeficiencies (ESID). Following genetic testing, diagnoses were further refined based on the most recent guidelines: Human Congenital Immunodeficiencies: 2024 Update of the International Union of Experts on the Classification of Diseases [13, 17, 18, 19]. Each patient's PID subtype, severity, and immuno-

logical profile were documented. Based on these assessments, individualized immunotherapy regimens were implemented.

Results:

The therapeutic strategies applied to Azerbaijani PID patients included the following:

Picture 1. The therapeutic strategies applied to Azerbaijani PID patients

1. Immunoglobulin Replacement Therapy:

We had 68 patients with antibody deficiencies aged 1–14 years. Immunoglobulin therapy was administered monthly to 48 pediatric patients and 4 adults above 18 years of age. Standard-dose IVIG (0.4 g/kg) was given to patients with IgG levels below 4 g/L. Treatment frequency ranged from monthly to biannual, depending on the clinical severity and IgG levels. Patients with moderately decreased IgG levels received IVIG once every two to three months under IgG monitoring. This therapy effectively reduced infections, hospitalizations, and organ damage, while improving quality of life and survival. The protocol demonstrated high efficacy and reduced patient mortality.

2. Bacterial Lysates and Cytokine Therapy:

Mucosal immune deficiencies were detected in 9 patients with selective IgA deficiency (5 diagnosed after age 8). Common complaints included frequent stomatitis, respiratory infections, and sinusitis (repeated more than 4–6 times per year). The mucosal immune system was supported using immunostimulants such as Imudon, Broncho-munal, and Lysozyme. These were also

prescribed to other PID patients with recurrent respiratory infections. Local antiseptics were used as adjunct therapies. This strategy reduced illness rates by 50%.

3. **Thymic Hormone and Immune-Stimulating Agents:** The second most common PID type was associated with a deficiency of total T lymphocytes or their subpopulations, due to congenital anatomical defects in thymus or thymic hormone synthesis insufficiency. Symptoms appeared at 1–3 months of life (e.g., convulsions, hypocalcemia, congenital heart defects, cleft palate). These children had high predisposition to viral, fungal and bacterial infections. For 6 patients with T-cell maturation defects (e.g., 4 children with Di-George syndrome), thymic peptides such as T-activin and Thymalin injections were administered to promote lymphocyte development. These were given daily at 0.1–0.2 mg/kg intramuscularly for the first 3 months, followed by T-cell monitoring and treatment adjustments. Therapy stopped convulsions, normalized calcium levels, and reduced frequency of infections. All patients are alive, the elder patient aged 13 (boy) and 11 (girl). Although T-cell levels remain below normal and there is some physical and mental developmental delay, their conditions are stable.

4. Antibiotic Prophylaxis and Treatment: Prophylactic and therapeutic antibiotics were administered to all PID patients, especially for respiratory infections. Broad-spectrum and prolonged courses were used depending on the infection profile and pathogen sensitivity. In acute episodes, targeted antimicrobial therapy was applied.

5. Antiviral and Supportive Therapies: The most common viral infections were Respiratory Syncytial Virus, Herpes Simplex Virus, and Epstein-Barr Virus (EBV). Fourteen patients with EBV-associated lymphoproliferative disorders were treated with Viferon, Likopid, β -glucan, and Lymphomyosot in combination to suppress viral replication and enhance host immunity.

6. Cytokine Analogues: In 2 patients with IL-12 pathway defects, recombinant interferon-gamma (Ingaron) was used to activate macrophages and enhance antiviral defense. However, due to limited clinical evidence, further studies are needed to assess long-term efficacy and safety.

7. Interferon and Growth Factor Therapy: For 4 patients with chronic granulomatous disease (CGD) and leukocyte deficiencies, interferon-gamma and hematopoietic growth factors were applied to improve immune cell function. All patients showed clinical improvement; skin lesions healed more effectively.

8. Hematopoietic Stem Cell Transplantation (HSCT): Currently, there are no HSCT facilities for PID patients in Azerbaijan. However, HSCT was pursued in select cases abroad for life-threatening immunodeficiencies, including 2 SCID patients and 1 patient with Wiskott–Aldrich syndrome, offering a potential cure.

Conclusion:

Most children with PID successfully underwent genetic testing and were reclassified. A significant proportion of patients were subsequently classified as patients with other types of PID due to the identification of a genetic cause for common immune deficiencies. This fact once again confirms the importance and necessity of conducting genetic studies at the early stages of the disease. Given the heterogeneity of primary immunodeficiencies, a precision medicine approach is imperative. Effective immunotherapy strategies must restore immune function, prevent infections, and enhance long-term outcomes and quality of life. Optimal management requires multidisciplinary collaboration among immunologists, pediatricians, rheumatologists, hematologists, allergists, neurologists, gastroenterologists, pulmonologists, and regional healthcare providers.

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